

Academic motivation and educational inclusion in university students in return to attendance

Motivación académica e inclusión educativa en estudiantes universitarios en el retorno a la asistencia

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Abstract

The objective of the study was to establish the relationship between academic motivation (AM) and the perception of educational inclusion of university students in return for attendance. The approach was quantitative, the type was descriptive correlational, and the sample consisted of 346 students to whom the EME 28 Educational Motivation Scale and the Inclusion Index were applied. According to the results, the correlations between the types of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation with the educational inclusion variable were positive and statistically significant, however, amotivation had a negative but significant correlation. In all cases, the effect size was large, greater than 0.50, while the statistical power was greater than 0.80 in all bivariate correlations. It was concluded that the students are motivated by the return to post-pandemic face-to-face activities but would consider that the higher education institution would have limitations to consolidate a model of educational inclusion, and the most vulnerable population could be affected.

Keywords: Higher education, inclusion, motivation, learning, students.

Resumen

El objetivo del estudio fue establecer la relación entre la motivación académica (MA) y la percepción hacia la inclusión educativa de los estudiantes universitarios en el retorno a la presencialidad. El enfoque fue cuantitativo y el tipo, descriptivo correlacional y la muestra estuvo conformada por 346 estudiantes a quienes se les aplicó la Escala de Motivación Educativa EME 28 y el Índice de Inclusión. De acuerdo con los resultados, las correlaciones entre los tipos de motivación intrínseca y extrínseca con la variable inclusión educativa fueron positivas y estadísticamente significativas, sin embargo, la amotivación tuvo una correlación negativa pero significativa. En todos los casos el tamaño del efecto fue grande superior a 0,50, mientras que la potencia estadística fue superior a 0,80 en todas las correlaciones bivariadas. Se concluyó que los estudiantes están motivados por el retorno a las actividades presenciales postpandemia pero considerarían que la institución de educación superior tendría limitaciones para consolidar un modelo de inclusión educativa, pudiendo quedar afectada la población más vulnerable.

Palabras clave: Educación superior, inclusión, motivación, aprendizaje, estudiantes.

Currently, the Peruvian Government has determined through regulations the end of virtual and remote classes exclusively, indicating the adoption of a model that combines face-to-face education with blended and virtual education, depending on the situation or need. This transition stage would correspond to the students having to adapt to face-to-face classes again, that is, the academic activities will have to be carried out on the university campus and stop using synchronous or asynchronous classes through information and communication technologies (ICT).

The coronavirus pandemic has been producing changes and problems in human activities, with education being one of the areas most affected by the administratively forced closure of educational institutions and the implementation of the distance education model as a solution to the crisis^{1,2}. The reality is that most universities were not prepared for such a sudden change, which represented a challenge for students and professors to deal with another modality of teaching and learning, because not all institutions could guarantee the ease of online learning³. This caused inconveniences such as adapting virtually to classes and synchronous evaluations, learning to use ICT tools such as E-learning, and misunderstanding, in many cases, that teachers must attend consultations and deliver assignments uninterrupted, among others⁴.

At the contextual level, the domain of human activity is different: education, recreation, work, etc., where personal and social factors play a very important role⁵. In the individual tendencies of each subject, there are situational factors that refer to the characteristics of the environment in which the subject finds himself and, together with the personal characteristics, would influence the final implication of the task⁶.

In university education, students must face a variety of challenges and achieve the academic goals necessary to successfully complete their training⁷. The main reasons that encourage students to study are related to learning, achieving success, avoiding failure, being valued, and obtaining results⁸.

The human being needs to use capacities, abilities, and skills previously acquired to achieve the proposed goals. Learning is defined as the process by which we modify and acquire skills, knowledge, behaviors, or values through various experiences, reasoning, and observations; so, it requires the activation of certain devices in the brain⁹.

The activation of these devices is called basic mental processes, they represent the majority of mental activities such as motivation, emotion, learning, attention, memory, perception, thought, and language, which fulfill specific tasks, different and fundamental, such as the motivation that, together with attention, represents the activating processes¹⁰. The term motivation derives from the Latin verb *moveré*, whose meaning is to move, therefore, motivation is the need to activate behavior by directing it towards the proposed goal⁶.

The proposals related to the conceptualization of motivation are different, defining it as a process that directs towards the

objective or goal of an activity that instigates and maintains it¹¹, fulfilling a motor role that leads students to adopt positive attitudes that allow them to learn in a more autonomous way¹². Likewise, it represents the disposition that, in general, the student may have to learn⁸. Therefore, motivation would be considered more than a product, not being directly observable, in which certain actions, efforts, persistence, and words that are carried out must be inferred¹¹; as well as external behaviors, which designate a series of variables that are related to both the direction of behavior and its intensity¹³.

Motivation includes several theories that support it as a set of processes involved in the activation, direction, and persistence of behavior aimed at achieving a goal or satisfying a need⁸. Theories involved in motivation, in addition to trying to define it, have sought to measure to identify the degrees or levels in which an individual could be located¹⁴. The theories state specifying their objectives which are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Contributions to the theory of motivation Source: López et al.¹⁴

Proposal	Author	Goal
Needs theory	David C. McClelland	It gives rise to three different types of motivation depending on the need to which it responds: achievement, power, and affiliation.
Equity theory	John Stacey Adams	Two influential elements: the relationship between what you require of your students (effort) and what you provide (reward), and the sense of fairness in using the same effort-reward relationship with the whole group (fairness).
X-Y theory	Douglas McGregor	The behavior of an individual is influenced by conditioning factors: Theory X, avoidance of work and obligation to do so; Theory Y, commitment to work in search of rewards for achievement.
Expectations theory	Víctor Vroom	It is proposed that motivation is a product of the value that the individual places on the possible results of their actions and the expectation that their goals will be met.
Goal setting theory	Edwin Locke	He points out that motivation has three factors: A high degree of difficulty: So that the goals are motivating and present a challenge. Degree of specificity: With clear and well-defined goals. Degree of participation of the individual: Establishment of their own goals.
Dual factor theory	Frederick Herzberg	Two types of factors that affect motivation: Intrinsic and motivational, they have a more personal and emotional origin. Extrinsic or hygienic: Product of the environment, context, and situations external to the person.

Unlike the previously proposed theories, the self-determination theory (SDT) addresses motivation from different aspects related to human activity. Therefore, it is proposed as a macro theory of motivation in which it is understood as the energy, direction, persistence, and purpose of behaviors, including intentions and actions¹⁵. The SDT recognizes different types

of motivation, along a continuum according to the degree of self-regulation of behavior, which operates at three levels of generality: global, contextual, and situational¹⁶.

Likewise, it has focused on the social and contextual conditions that facilitate self-motivation and psychological development, postulating as psychological needs: competence, autonomy, and relationship, once satisfied, improve self-motivation and mental health, but when frustrated, decrease motivation and welfare¹⁷.

This perspective posits that behavior can be intrinsically motivated, extrinsically motivated, or amotivated, lying along a continuum from self-determination to lack of control¹⁸. Intrinsic motivation is typical of the individual and his commitment, being the activity the reinforcer itself, where personal interests propitiate the tendency to seek and overcome challenges, with autonomy, interest, and curiosity; extrinsic motivation, would be the reinforcer, manipulated from the outside, focuses on the elements of the environment, causes individuals to participate in the activity¹⁹. In other words, extrinsic motivation comes into play when an individual uses activity as a means to an end. However, intrinsic motivation comes into play when an individual performs an activity for their satisfaction¹⁰.

Just as students are motivated, there is also demotivation, which predominates in adolescence and higher education, so it is thought that motivated students learn faster and more effectively than unmotivated students¹³. This way, amotivation sits at the lowest level of autonomy in a continuum of different types of motivation and occurs when contingencies between actions and their consequences are not perceived²⁰. This is due to the lack of intention of the students to achieve their goals, which increases negative thoughts about their ability to successfully complete the assigned work¹².

Therefore, types of motivation can suggest different reasons why people act in a certain way depending on different types of regulation and causal trajectories of behavior²¹. This means that humans can be active and engaged, or passive and aloof, depending largely on the social conditions in which they develop and function¹⁷.

On the other hand, educational inclusion, its main objective is to work on the educational phenomenon in its entirety, with the ultimate intention of having an impact on a social model of Human Rights, since it is not enough to transmit knowledge, but it is essential to promote a doctrinal change and ideological, in relation to the conception of diversity and people with disabilities, trying to guarantee a fundamental right: the right to education, a right that implicitly includes inclusive education²². It maintains that all human beings are different, they must live together and have the opportunity to carry out training and professional projects with social equality.

It is comprised of three dimensions of an inclusive culture, understood as the collaborative organization plans and spaces that bring together within a single framework all the support modalities to attend to the diversity of the student body, the inclusive practices, related to the generation of a community that develops shared inclusive values by what to do for fac-

ulty, students, school board members, and families; finally, to inclusive policies, understood as actions that reflect the culture and inclusive policies of the school, which situate the possibilities of change within the educational environment and the regular classroom to overcome the barriers to learning and participation²³. The need for a higher education institution to respond to the purpose of the previously proposed dimensions would be based on the heterogeneity of students because not all have the same way of learning, considering that learning difficulties depend not only on certain types of cognitive problems, language, reading, arithmetic, but also movement, family conditions, among others.

The purpose would be inclined to ensure that students interact in a positive social environment, it would involve assuming, as a university community, a structured organization, a culture oriented towards a diverse approach, with teaching practices and the necessary supports that promote the participation of all students²⁴. The change would cover all the areas of the institution, from the governing bodies, the classroom environment, policies, regulations, actions, and programs that make it possible to eliminate obstacles and reduce difficulties in achieving equal conditions for university students. Likewise, it would mean the consolidation of new values represented in equal opportunities aimed at a quality education that, in contrast to traditional education, favors cooperation and learning environments fluctuate around the needs of students²⁵.

Higher education students after two years of virtual or remote participation in synchronous and asynchronous classes, in some cases, may have acquired certain skills and rhythms for learning, somewhat more autonomous as opposed to face-to-face studies, while in others cases would have had learning difficulties, due to the acquisition of digital skills, cognitive or developmental limitations that are feasible to face through the active strategy of cooperative learning that is easy to apply in face-to-face classes. At the Universidad Nacional Amazónica de Madre de Dios (UNAMAD), located in the southeast of the Peruvian Amazon, it has been arranged that the stipulated adaptation period, based on government regulations, that in the development of the first academic semester of the year 2022 the modality will be virtual for the first four cycles, while, from the fifth cycle onwards, the study modality will be face-to-face.

The purpose of the research was to establish the relationship between academic motivation and the perception of educational inclusion of university students in the return to attendance.

Materials and methods

The research is framed within the quantitative, descriptive correlational study. The questionnaires were applied in a single moment time to the established sample, corresponding to a cross-sectional design. The student population was made up of all the students enrolled in the first academic cycle of the year 2022, making a total of 3474 students. To obtain the sample, the population was divided according to the faculties,

with 1128 students from the Faculty of Ecotourism representing 32%, in the Faculty of Education 1320 corresponding to 38% were counted and for the Faculty of Engineering, they were 1026 equal to 30% of the total. Likewise, to obtain the sample, simple random sampling was applied, being made up of 346 students, of which 112 corresponded to the Faculty of Ecotourism, 131 to the Faculty of Education, and 102 to the Faculty of Engineering.

Regarding the data collection instrument used to measure the degree and type of motivation, the Educational Motivation Scale EME 28 was used, it has the purpose of identifying the type of motivation that predominates in the students (extrinsic, intrinsic, amotivation), it is composed of 28 items, of which 12 of them measure internal motivation, another 12, external motivation, and 4, amotivation. The scale and indices range from: does not correspond at all (1) to totally corresponds. Finally, to measure the educational inclusion variable, the Inclusion Index²³ was used, which evaluates the inclusive culture through 31 items, the inclusive practices composed of 14 items, and the inclusive policies with 17 items.

To obtain the results regarding the type of motivation that predominates in university students, as well as the perception of educational inclusion in the university, descriptive statistics were used, representing the analysis and results of the academic motivation variable in a bar diagram, while for the variable educational inclusion, the representation of the results was made in a circular diagram. On the other hand, the correlation findings were obtained using Spearman's Rho because the variables are ordinal. Likewise, to corroborate the alternating hypotheses, the size of the effect represented as a minimum measure $p=0.50$ and the statistical power, which

as a minimum criterion must be $1-\beta=0.80$ to be accepted, were used. Considering that, to estimate the size of the effect, it responds to the magnitude of the differences found in the study, and the statistical power, which response to the degree of validity of the research findings²⁶.

Results

The information provided in figure 1 presents the results, comparatively, between the three types of motivation: intrinsic (IM), extrinsic (EM), and amotivation, as well as the subtypes that compose them. The majority of university students present a high level of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation; however, the IM has 1.3% less than the EM. Secondly, the existence of a percentage of the sample of students who fall within the low amotivation type can be confirmed with 72% while the remaining 28% would correspond to the medium and high levels.

In figure 2, the results of the perception of the educational inclusion of the university students are presented, having obtained as results that 51.9% of the student body has a regular perception, 42.9% considers that the form of inclusion that represents the culture, the educational practice and policy is adequate, while 5.2% of university students classify it as inadequate. Based on the information found, it could be considered that, according to the perception of the students, the university institution would not be fully prepared to adopt an inclusive model in reference to practices, policies, and culture or, if it already had it, it would not it would reach to be totally rooted, as to be considered as part of the work of the student body. This difficulty could cause problems and limitations in

Figure 1. Type of motivation in relation to its degree of predominance

the learning, adaptation, and maintenance of the most vulnerable student population.

Discussion

The results shown in Figure 1 are revalidated by Carrillo¹², who concludes that more than half of the students have a medium and high level of motivation with 91.1% for IM and 87.7% for EM. As well Salamea y Cedillo²⁷, refer that the set of university students reached the high level in motivation with a score that ranges between 77.8% and 90%. Likewise, Casanova et al.²⁸ identified that 85% of the students obtained a high degree of intrinsic motivation, while 67%, had a high degree of extrinsic motivation. While Llanes et al.²⁹ indicate regarding the most frequent type of motivation in the students, that most of them showed a profile in which the sum of the intrinsic motives turned out to be higher than the extrinsic ones; this difference being statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 2. Perception of educational inclusión

In the analysis of the bivariate correlations presented in Table 2, the results that support the significant positive relationship are specified in the first place, between the type of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation with the dimensions: culture, practices, policies, as well as with the variable inclusive education. These results would indicate that students who are motivated could perceive educational inclusion from its dimensions of culture, practices, and inclusive policies. The information obtained would be similar to the correlation obtained between the type of EM with the educational inclusion variable. The opposite occurs in the data obtained from the relationship between the amotivation type with educational inclusion due to being inverse. Secondly, to corroborate the information presented above, the results obtained showed that the effect size was greater than 0.50 for the correlations made, so it would be considered a large size and in terms of statistical power, the results were higher than 0.80, being able to explain that the perception of the students in relation to educational inclusion would be intervened in part by the type of intrinsic, extrinsic or amotivation motivation.

These findings would explain that the student's motivation to pursue his studies responds to personal attributions towards learning, which include variables such as university experience, personal expectations, family, future, independence, access to the job market, profession, aid, responsibility, inner well-being, improvement, the importance of knowledge, vocation, among others³⁰. This refers to the fact that university students, being motivated, would integrate affective, cognitive, and behavioral components to encourage them to carry out their activities, including study³¹. However, the demotivation of the student for his profession would be due to the educational processes, the knowledge that is imparted to him, or the misinformation that he has about the career, the economic aspect, and the few job opportunities that are offered³². In the same way, it can be considered another indicator of amotivation with the capacity for socialization. Sánchez et al.³³ identified that reserved students have a higher level of amotivation than the more communicative students on a social level. This information would support that a small part of the sample is losing interest in recovering face-to-face studies.

The results presented on figure 2 are corroborated by Cruz³⁴, who would support the reasons for the position of university students inclined to an unfavorable perception of educational inclusion, due to the pressure exerted academically on them, causing difficulties in the delivery of tasks, class participation, allowing to be evaluated again, field practices, graduating and graduating. This problem is due to the need to establish a common and agreed definition of inclusive education and address the main shortcomings and problems of the educational system, such as promoting teacher training in terms of inclusion and disability, as well as the adaptation and implementation of a curricular design, in accordance with the precepts of inclusion^{22,35,36}. There are limitations to maintaining an idea of educational inclusion from a holistic view that contemplates solutions from various perspectives in which the inclusive training of teachers has an essential priority³⁷. Maintaining the gap between exclusion and inclusion marked by inequality in access to resources and care that people with disabilities require to maintain adequate pursuit within university careers³⁸.

Table 2. Correlations between the types of motivation with the inclusive education variable and its dimensions

Variables		Inclusive culture	Inclusive practices	Inclusive policies	Inclusive education
Intrinsic motivation	Spearman's Rho	0.493	0.505	0.477	0.541
	Sig.	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
	<i>p</i>	0.702	0.710	0.690	0.736
	1-β	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999
Extrinsic motivation	Spearman's Rho	0.406	0.468	0.391	0.463
	Sig.	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
	<i>p</i>	0.637	0.684	0.625	0.680
	1-β	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999
Amotivation	Spearman's Rho	-0.418	-0.427	-0.423	-0.526
	Sig.	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
	<i>p</i>	0.646	0.653	0.650	0.725
	1-β	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999

Conclusion

Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation were positioned at a high level, however, with EM only 1.3% higher than IM. Unlike the first two types, amotivation was at the low level of 72%, which would represent that students are motivated after returning to attendance. In the second place, educational inclusion in the university obtained an assessment of 51.9%, placing the perception of the student body at the regular level. Finally, the correlations between the types of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation with the educational inclusion variable were positive and significant, unlike the amotivation type, which had a negative but also significant correlation. In all cases, the effect size was greater than 0.50, while the statistical power was greater than 0.80 in all bivariate correlations. The results obtained would indicate that the students are motivated by the return to post-pandemic face-to-face activities but would consider that the higher education institution would have limitations to consolidate a model of educational inclusion, which could affect the most vulnerable population.

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